

1 **HIV infection in Kupffer cells.**

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7 HIV-1 infection of Kupffer cells of the liver resulted in activation of the innate immune receptor *NOD2*
8 concomitant with activation of the viral sensor and *NOD2* target *ZBP1*. Kupffer cell HIV infection activated
9 interferon signaling pathway-wide (*IFIT1*, *IFIT2*, *IFITM3*, *GBP5*) and resulted in induction of *CCL8* and
10 *IL3RA1*. Interestingly, Kupffer cells silenced *TIMP3* while activating the homeobox *HESX* following HIV-1
11 infection.

12 Citations

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